

COMPONENTS OF SPEECH ETIQUETTE IN MODERN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS

*D. Istamova*¹

Abstract:

The article discusses the problems that arise from ignorance of the norms of speech etiquette. Ignorance of speech etiquette can lead to public reproach or even lead to conflict. In order to avoid this, it is necessary to master the norms of speech etiquette. And for those who study English, this topic is especially relevant due to some differences in the norms of address.

Key words: form of appeal, etiquette, speech etiquette, communication norms

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Introduction

There is probably no linguistic culture in which there are no requirements for the norms of speech etiquette. We can say that speech etiquette has an ancient history. As for primitive times, ritual actions were represented by speech etiquette. A word is not just a set of letters and sounds; a word expresses special meanings associated with magical and ritual performances, the relationship between people and cosmic power. And therefore, speech activity reflects the influence, as primitive people believed, on animals and the surrounding world.

Of course, over time, there is a change in speech etiquette and its place in modern society. These changes are associated with mythological and religious beliefs, ideas about immutable social hierarchies, etc.

Materials and methods

It is clearly visible that in every nation some similar traditions and foundations can be identified. For example, probably in every nation there are certain forms of greetings and farewells, respectful addresses to elders, etc.

Speech etiquette presupposes compliance with norms of behavior and communication. Speech etiquette represents the developed rules of speech behavior, a system of speech formulas for communication. A person who masters speech etiquette gains authority, inspires trust and respect. Knowledge of the norms of speech etiquette and, of course, their observance helps a person gain confidence, ease, a person does not have to feel awkward due to minor violations or incorrect actions, a person gets the opportunity to avoid ridicule from others. Speech etiquette includes certain constructions, for example, constructions of expressing requests; who differently focus on politeness in communication, which in turn regulates the interaction of partners. Depending on the situation, the design of addresses is chosen: in formal and informal conversation, neutrality of the situation, deliberately polite or average tone, in conversations with acquaintances and strangers, etc. And the task is to choose the appropriate form of address in a given situation, which, in turn, will show the level of culture and mastery of speech etiquette.

¹ *Istamova D.S., PhD, Navoi State Pedagogical Institute*

Results and discussion

It is worth noting that etiquette has been studied most deeply in linguistics, where etiquette is considered a functional-semantic microcircuit of linguistic units, which is tied to standard situations. These units are socially defined and nationally specific, regulating the requirements of speech behavior.

The rules of speech etiquette show both general and special national-specific ideas about politeness and can impose a ban on speech patterns that are unacceptable from an ethical point of view. Speech etiquette is implemented at various language levels: lexical and phraseological, grammatical, stylistic, intonation, spelling, organizational and communicative. Knowledge of speech etiquette is important not only for the English themselves, it is important for all students of English as a foreign language. English speech etiquette is unique and has its own rules and norms, which, however, significantly diverge from the rules and norms, for example, of Russian speech etiquette. This can lead to the fact that even a very cultured Russian person will be impolite among the English if he, while communicating with them in their language, does not know English speech etiquette. In the same way, an English gentleman may seem impolite when communicating in Russian with cultural

Russian, if he has not studied Russian speech etiquette.

Before traveling to the UK, you should first become familiar with the norms of behavior in English society. A more accessible object for comparison with our usual concepts of norms is, first of all, English speech etiquette.

The word please, which in Russian usage is appropriate in almost any convenient and inconvenient situation, also changes significantly in English. Probably only in a request it corresponds to the English expression please. Inserting the word please into your response to someone's gratitude, apology, etc. In such situations, the polysemy of the cliché is expressed by a number of English clichés: That's all right; Never mind; Don't mention it; line it is; Help yourself; Not at all; Certainly; Why not?, etc.

A distinctive feature of national English thinking is the absence of direct judgments and direct expression of one's opinion. For example, instead of: You are wrong or I disagree with you, an Englishman will say: I am afraid, you are not quite right. I'm afraid you're not entirely right or: I am afraid, I cannot agree with you - I'm afraid I can't agree with you. Instead of saying you're lying or I don't believe you, an Englishman will prefer a polite remark: You have been very economical with the truth - You were very economical in truthfully presenting the facts. If on the continent they can say: You are a liar, Sir, and rather a dirty one - You are a liar, sir, and quite dirty, in England it will sound: Oh, is that so? - Does this really happen? or: That is rather an unusual story, isn't it?

Thus, the main values of English culture are most often called individualism, rationalism, independence, pragmatism, competition, equality, traditionalism, tolerance. These characteristics play an important role, because reflected in the lifestyle, interpersonal relationships and behavior of the British. A distinctive feature of national English thinking is the absence of direct judgments, direct expression of one's opinion, and positive thinking.

But expressions of disrespect or even disrespect are possible in English society. There are even special verbs that mean "to show disrespect to someone/something by ridiculing, grinning contemptuously": sneer, scoff, jeer, gird, flout, gibe/jibe, flier, taunt, twit, mock, ridicule, deride. The differential features of these words are "viciously" (ridicule, deride, taunt, sneer), "cruelly"

(twit), “offensively” (scoff), “cynically, rudely” (sneer, jeer, gird), “gloatingly” (taunt), “contrary to the norms of behavior” (mock, taunt), “humiliating” (ridicule), “loudly” (jeer), “grimacing” (fleece), “with a crooked grin” (sneer), “with contempt laughing” (deride), “mocking” (mock, taunt, twit, gibe), “sometimes good-naturedly” (gibe) (WNDS, SBED, LDCE, RHD) [1].

A negative attitude in the form of formulaic disclosure can also be seen in a short, caustic or incredulous question. For example: “Mr. Starr has denied the allegation of his previous contact with the committee.” - “Has he?” It is this form that is considered the highest degree of distrust or expression of a negative attitude towards the interlocutor and his statement. But, of course, you should not omit such points as intonation and individual characteristics of your interlocutors.

But still, it would be a huge mistake not to show such an important characteristic of behavior in conflict situations in English society as shifting the blame onto oneself. This characteristic can be seen in the phrase “It’s my fault.” A person’s guilt is recognized immediately in communication. This is done so that the interlocutor generously admits his own guilt. Then the conflict situation comes down to a competition in nobility. This is a purely English style of behavior.

In other words, communication is carried out for the sake of communication; it is consciously or usually unconsciously aimed at establishing or maintaining contact. In general, such speeches are standard and minimally informative. However, the informative nature of such conversations does not mean that these conversations are not needed by people and society as a whole. As a contact-establishing function of speech etiquette, we can give an example of the English talking about the weather [2]:

Olivia: Hello!

Thomas: Hi, Tina. It's Joe. Olivia: Hi Joe.

Thomas: What's the weather like today? Olivia: It's so wet and miserable.

Thomas: We really need some sunshine, don't we? Another example:

- What's the forecast for tonight? - It's supposed to be really cold. It's going to be minus 15.

From the above examples, it becomes obvious that we are faced with not just models of polite communication, but the creation of a comfortable atmosphere, the desire to “bridge” and somehow fill an awkward pause, this is a culture of communication. It is not recommended to immediately discuss the financial crisis or the appearance of singer Elton John. The great theme of weather captivates everyone: the plumber who comes to the house to fix the tap, the owner of the sausage shop, and the taxi driver who drives you through London traffic jams.

Another function of speech etiquette is the regulation of relationships, which consists in adjusting existing relationships, but not positive enough for further successful communication. The effect of this function can be seen in the examples of verbal communication formulas with apologies. The English language offers several apology formulas [4]:

In official speech or correspondence, the lexeme “apologize” is used: Please accept my apologies.

In colloquial semi-formal speech, the word “Sorry” is used: The teacher looks into the staff room in search of a colleague:

- Lily?

- She is not here at the moment. I have not seen her. Sorry.

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Conclusion

Summarizing the above, we can hope that having mastered the norms and techniques of speech etiquette, participants in communication will avoid many conflict situations, achieve mutual understanding, and earn respectful treatment without offending their partner. When communicating, the speech of the interlocutors must follow certain rules of conversation, otherwise the interlocutors will not come to a consensus. Communication, treatment and behavior in general must follow the specific rules of a particular sociocultural affiliation. It can be added that the norms of speech etiquette are an integral part of any national culture. Speech behavior reflects the tradition, life experience, thinking, mentality and way of life of any nation.

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